

Non-immunogenic Microenvironmental Factors Effect on Tumor Growth With Immune Response

Ibrahim Mu'awiyya Idris^{1*}, Ibrahim Lawal Kane²

¹Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina, Nigeria. Orchid iD: [0000-0002-1721-0923](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1721-0923)

²Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Umaru Musa Yar'adua University, Katsina, Nigeria. ORCID iD: [0000-0001-5206-0716](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5206-0716)

Received: 20 Sep 2020

Accepted: 30 Nov 2020

Published Online: 31 Dec 2020

Abstract: The non-immunogenic micro-environmental factors effect on tumor growth system modeled by correlated additive and multiplicative colored noises with colored cross correlation under the immune influence is studied. The Novikov theorem, Fox approach and the Ansatz of Hanggi is used to obtain an approximate Fokker Planck equation for the transition probability $p(x, t|x', t')$ of which the corresponding steady state (equilibrium) distribution $P_{st}(x)$ for the tumor growth system exist. We find that the correlation time strength τ and the immune strength λ have opposite effects on both the steady state distribution $P_{st}(x)$ and the mean $\langle x \rangle_{st}$ of the tumor population, with increase in correlation time strength τ promoting growth and increase in the immune response strength λ reducing growth. The result further indicated that the stronger the immune response λ , the weaker the effect of correlation time strength τ on the tumor growth system

Key words: Fokker-Planck Equation, Colored Noise, Tumor-immune Interaction.

1. Introduction

In the recent decades, application of stochastic methods to the study of random system has been a great success especially in the field biology, chemistry and physics. Research in [1] first discovered that correlated effect in random systems modeled by simultaneous additive and multiplicative noises effect would reveal an additional interesting properties for the system under study. Subsequently, stochastic models of random systems driven by more than one noise sources with common origin as reported in several communications considered the correlated effect between noises, and which in turn reveals many counter-intuitive phenomena such as the noise induced transport, noise induce transition, phase transition and noise induced resonance [2–4]. Moreover, correlated noise effect has been the interest in the theoretical study of many biological and physical systems [5–11]. In literature, the application of stochastic methods in the dynamical study of tumor growth have been given considerable attention especially in tumor response to external therapy such as radiotherapy and chemotherapy [12], while some communications consider theoretical investigation of tumor growth in the presence of immune response [13–16, 23].

Tumor growth system is an open biological phenomenon that responds to influences from within the immediate tumor microenvironmental components which are either pro-malignant, anti-malignant or sometimes neutral to malignancy [17]. Several communications revealed that components of tumor microenvironment have

a significant role in tumor initiation and progression [18–20]. Tumor growth among other diseases can be investigated theoretically and the corresponding numerical result will give a good insight into the dynamical complexities of the diseases [12, 31]. Moreover, tumor microenvironment is such a complex environment that has a double-edge effect on tumor growth dynamics of either promoting growth or inhibiting growth depending on many conditions and factors [17, 30]. In this paper, we consider the effect due to tumor interaction with the surrounding non-immunogenic microenvironmental components in the presence of immune response [21], and such microenvironmental components include among others extracellular matrix proteins, fibroblast cells, signal transduction pathways, immunity and nutrients. Fluctuations of the non-immunogenic microenvironmental components within the tumor site modeled by additive colored noise will affect the tumor growth and decay parameters generating a multiplicative colored noise, such that the two noises are correlated having originated from the same source. The paper is structured as follows, section 2 presents the tumor model in the form of Langevin equation with logistic model accounting for deterministic growth pattern, section 3 present the analytic expression for the steady state distribution of the tumor growth system, section 4 discuss the numerical results and section 5 concludes the paper with acknowledgement.

2. Theoretical Model

The theoretical model for the tumor growth system $x(t)$ with immune response where x and t stands for spatial and temporal variables respectively is given by

$$\dot{x}(t) = f(x) - \Phi(x), \quad (1)$$

the over dot in Eq. (1) represent derivative with respect to time, $f(x)$ is the logistic growth equation and $\Phi(x)$ is the tumor-immune interaction potential

$$f(x) = \alpha x - \beta x^2, \quad (2)$$

$$\Phi(x) = \frac{\lambda x^2}{1 + x^2}. \quad (3)$$

Thus, Eq. (1) represent the deterministic theoretical model equation for tumor growth in the presence of immune response, where α is the growth constant and β is the decay constant which in addition is supplemented with the tumor-immune interaction potential $\Phi(x)$, and λ is some constant measuring the strength of the immunity [13]. Theoretical study of tumor growth is such a heuristic approach where some mathematical equations that closely captures the general features of tumor growth, and as well their ability to fit experimental data are considered as deterministic models. The most popularly used deterministic models for microbial cell growth, and particularly tumor cell growth in literature is the logistic sigmoid equation, [13, 22]. Consequently, with Eq's. (1)-(3), the stochastic model equation for tumor response to the non-immunogenic microenvironmental factors within the neighborhood of the tumor cells in the presence of immunity is given by

$$\dot{x}(t) = \alpha x - \left(\beta + \frac{\lambda}{1 + x^2} \right) x^2 + x\xi(t) + \zeta(t), \quad (4)$$

where x is the state variable representing growth and assume strictly positive values $x \geq 0$. Moreover $\xi(t)$ and $\zeta(t)$ are the multiplicative and additive colored Gaussian noises with the following properties

$$\langle \xi(t) \rangle = \langle \zeta(t) \rangle = 0, \quad (5)$$

$$\langle \xi(t)\xi(t') \rangle = \frac{2D}{\tau_1} \exp\left(-\frac{t-t'}{\tau_1}\right), \quad (6)$$

$$\langle \zeta(t)\zeta(t') \rangle = \frac{2\sigma}{\tau_2} \exp\left(-\frac{t-t'}{\tau_2}\right). \quad (7)$$

We also consider colored cross-correlation between $\xi(t)$ and $\zeta(t)$ given by

$$\langle \xi(t)\zeta(t') \rangle = \langle \zeta(t)\xi(t') \rangle = \frac{2\phi\sqrt{\sigma D}}{\tau_3} \exp\left(-\frac{|t-t'|}{\tau_3}\right), \quad (8)$$

where D and σ are the strength of $\xi(t)$ and $\zeta(t)$ respectively, and ϕ is the strength of the correlation between multiplicative noise $\xi(t)$ and additive noise $\zeta(t)$ under the condition that $[0 \leq \phi < 1]$. The deterministic potential function corresponding to Eq. (1) is given by

$$U(x) = \frac{\beta x^3}{3} - \frac{\alpha x^2}{2} + \lambda x - \lambda \tan^{-1} x. \quad (9)$$

The potential $U(x)$ is depicted in Figure 1, and has two stable states $x_{s-} = 0$ and $x_{s+} = 1$, and one unstable

Figure 1. The effective potential $U(x)$ against the tumor cell number x with parameter values $a = 1.0$, $b = 0.1$ and $\lambda = 0.4$.

state $x_u \approx 0.6$. Moreover, it is biologically obvious that x_{s-} represent the tumor free state (state of extinction), and x_{s+} represent the maximum growth state for the tumor. Furthermore, the tumor growth is subject to the surrounding tumor microenvironmental factors effect, and tumor within the neighborhood of unstable growth state x_u will move in the direction of either one of the stable states x_{s-} or x_{s+} in the presence of influence, but the direction of movement depends on the nature and circumstance of the influential force.

3. Steady State (Equilibrium) Distribution

The corresponding stochastic Liouville's equation for Eq. (1) is given by

$$\partial_t p(x, t) = -\partial_x \{f(x) + g_1(x)\xi(t) + g_2(x)\zeta(t)\} p(x, t), \quad (10)$$

where $\rho(x, t)$ is the probability density function representing ensemble of systems for the possible realizations of the stochastic forces $\xi(t)$ and $\zeta(t)$ respectively, and by Van Kampen lemma [24]

$$P(x, t) = \langle p(x, t) \rangle, \quad (11)$$

where in Eq. (10), $p(x, t)$ represent a realization of a single tumor cell trajectory and is given by

$$p(x, t) = \delta(x(t) - x). \quad (12)$$

The probability function $P(x, t)$ represent the ensemble average taking over the distribution of many $p(x, t)$ for the possible realizations of $\xi(t)$ and $\zeta(t)$ respectively, and of which we further re-write Eq. (10) as

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t P(x, t) = & -\partial_x f(x) P(x, t) - \partial_x g_1(x) \langle \xi(t) \delta(x(t) - x) \rangle \\ & - \partial_x g_2(x) \langle \zeta(t) \delta(x(t) - x) \rangle. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

For the ensemble averages $\langle \dots \rangle$ in Eq. (13), we consider the Novikov, Ronald Fox and Ansatz of Hanggi approaches to derive the approximate Fokker-Planck equation in the steady state regime [27–29]

$$\begin{aligned} \partial_t P(x, t) = & -\partial_x f(x) P(x, t) + \frac{D}{M_1} \partial_x g_1(x) \partial_x g_1(x) P(x, t) + \frac{\sigma}{M_2} \partial_x g_2(x) \partial_x g_2(x) P(x, t) \\ & + \frac{2\phi\sqrt{\sigma D}}{M_3} [\partial_x g_1(x) \partial_x g_2(x) + \partial_x g_2(x) \partial_x g_1(x)] P(x, t), \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

and

$$M_i = 1 - \tau_i \left[f(x_s)' - \frac{g_i(x_s)'}{g_i(x_s)} f(x_s) \right], \quad i = 1, 2, 3. \quad (15)$$

where $x_s = (\alpha/\beta)$ is the steady state value for the function $f(x)$ and τ_i are the associated correlation times respectively. In addition, Eq. (14) is only valid under the condition that $M_i, i=1, 2, 3$ are strictly positive, i.e., $M_i > 0$, and we can re-write Eq. (1) as

$$\dot{x}(t) = f(x) + x\xi(t) + \zeta(t). \quad (16)$$

Interpreting Eq. (16) using Eq. (14) and (15) in the sense of Stratonovich, an Approximate Fokker Planck equation is obtained, thus

$$\partial_t P(x, t) = -\partial_x A(x) P(x, t) + \partial_{xx} B(x) P(x, t), \quad (17)$$

where $A(x)$ and $B(x)$ in Eq. (17) are the modified drift and diffusion terms

$$A(x) = \left(\alpha + \frac{D}{1 + \alpha\tau_1} \right) x - \left(\beta + \frac{\lambda}{1 + x^2} \right) x^2 + \frac{\phi\sqrt{\sigma D}}{1 + \alpha\tau_3}, \quad (18)$$

$$B(x) = \frac{D}{1 + \alpha\tau_1} x^2 + \frac{2\phi\sqrt{\sigma D}}{1 + \alpha\tau_3} x + \frac{\sigma}{1 + \alpha\tau_2}. \quad (19)$$

An explicit expression for the steady state (equilibrium) distribution $P_{st}(x)$ corresponding to Eq. (17) with reflecting boundary condition is obtained, [25, 26]

$$P_{st}(x) = \frac{N}{B(x)} \exp[-V(x)/D], \quad (20)$$

where N is the normalization constant choosing to normalize the steady state (equilibrium) distribution $P_{st}(x)$ such that

$$\int_0^{\infty} P_{st}(x) dx = 1, \quad (21)$$

$V(x)$ in Eq. (20) is the effective potential for the acting forces

$$\begin{aligned} V(x) = [\beta x + \lambda(1 + \alpha\tau) \arctan(x)] - E \ln \left| \left(\frac{Dx + \phi\sqrt{\sigma D}}{\sqrt{\sigma D(1 - \phi^2)}} \right)^2 + 1 \right| \\ + \frac{F}{\sqrt{\sigma D(1 - \phi^2)}} \arctan \left(\frac{Dx + \phi\sqrt{\sigma D}}{\sqrt{\sigma D(1 - \phi^2)}} \right), \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where

$$E = \frac{\alpha(1 + \alpha\tau) + D}{2} + \phi\sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{D}} \left(\beta + \frac{\lambda D}{Q} \right), \quad (23)$$

$$F = \left[\alpha(1 + \alpha\tau) + 2 \left(\beta + \frac{\lambda D}{Q} \right) \phi\sqrt{\frac{\sigma}{D}} \right] \phi\sqrt{\sigma D} + \sigma \left(\beta + \frac{\lambda D}{Q} \right) (1 + \alpha\tau), \quad (24)$$

$$Q = D + \frac{D\phi}{\sqrt{1 - \phi^2}}. \quad (25)$$

The mean of the steady state distribution for the tumor population $x(t)$ is determined numerically from the equation

$$\langle x \rangle_{st} = \int_0^{\infty} x P_{st}(x) dx. \quad (26)$$

where $P_{st}(x)$ is the steady state (equilibrium) distribution given in Eq. (20). The increase in the mean $\langle x \rangle_{st}$ value of the tumor population indicates that the tumor is growing, while the decrease indicates that the tumor is approaching extinction.

4. Numerical Results and Discussion

From the numerical result of Eq. (20), we analyze the effect of non-immunogenic tumor microenvironmental factors on the steady state distribution $P_{st}(x)$ of tumor population under the action of immune response. Figure 2 show the effect of varying strength of the tumor response parameter D on the steady state distribution $P_{st}(x)$, it is observed that increasing D results to decreasing the value of $P_{st}(x)$ and the extrema shifting to smaller tumor population respectively, and since x in Figure 2 denote the tumor cell population (the extrema corresponds to the most probable distribution). This indicates that the non-immunogenic tumor microenvironmental factors effects within the tumor site may inhibit tumor growth. Furthermore, Figure 3

Figure 2. Plot of the steady state (equilibrium) distribution $P_{st}(x)$ against the tumor population x at varying D . Remaining parameter values are fixed at $\lambda = 0.1$, $\sigma = 0.5$, $\tau = 0.5$, $\phi = 0.6$, $\alpha = 1.0$, $\beta = 0.1$ (units are arbitrary).

Figure 3. Plot of the steady state (equilibrium) distribution $P_{st}(x)$ against the tumor population x at varying λ . Remaining parameter values are fixed at $D = 1.0$, $\sigma = 0.5$, $\tau = 0.3$, $\phi = 0.6$, $\alpha = 1.0$, $\beta = 0.1$ (units are arbitrary).

show the effect of the strength of the immune response λ on the steady state distribution $P_{st}(x)$, and it is seen that increasing λ changes the position of the extrema of $P_{st}(x)$ and since x denote the tumor population, then this indicates that the strength λ pushes the steady state distribution $P_{st}(x)$ of the tumor population towards extinction. Figure 4 depict the effect of correlation time τ on the steady state distribution $P_{st}(x)$, it is observed from Figure 4(a) that increasing τ moves the extrema of the steady state distribution $P_{st}(x)$ from small tumor population to large tumor population, which in other word corresponds to enhancing tumor growth. However, in Figures 4(b) - 4(d), the strength of the immune response λ is increased, that is $\lambda = 2.0$, 4.0 and 8.0 respectively, and keeping all other parameter values the same as in Figure 4(a), it is observed that the extrema of the steady state distribution $P_{st}(x)$ shifts toward smaller tumor population at increasing λ with increased probability. This indicates that an effective and sufficient immune response within the tumor microenvironment will subdue the growth effects exerted by the surrounding non-immunogenic component of tumor microenvironment, and can even reduce tumor population towards extinction. Furthermore, the effect of

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 4. (a) Plot of the steady state (equilibrium) distribution $P_{st}(x)$ against the tumor population x at varying τ with $\lambda = 0.5$ (b) Plot of the steady state (equilibrium) distribution $P_{st}(x)$ against the tumor population x at varying τ with $\lambda = 2.0$ (c) Plot of the steady state (equilibrium) distribution $P_{st}(x)$ against the tumor population x at varying τ with $\lambda = 4.0$ (d) Plot of the steady state (equilibrium) distribution $P_{st}(x)$ against the tumor population x at varying τ with $\lambda = 8.0$. Remaining parameter values are fixed at $D = 1.0$, $\sigma = 0.5$, $\phi = 0.6$, $\alpha = 1.0$, $\beta = 0.1$ (units are arbitrary).

the immune response λ on the mean $\langle x \rangle_{st}$ is shown in Figure 6, with the increase in λ resulting to the decrease in the mean value of the tumor population as seen in Figure 6(a). Moreover, it is also observed from Figure 6(b) that the effect of the correlation time τ on the mean $\langle x \rangle_{st}$ of the tumor population is less effective in the presence of adequate immune response λ . In contrast, the results in Figures 5 and 6 indicated that the strength of the immune response λ and the correlation time strength τ have opposite effect on both the steady state distribution $P_{st}(x)$ and the mean $\langle x \rangle_{st}$ of the tumor population, with increased in λ value reducing growth while increased in τ value enhancing growth.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5. (a) Plot of the mean $\langle x \rangle_{st}$ against the tumor population x at varying τ . Remaining parameter values are fixed at $\lambda = 1.0$, $D = 2.0$, $\sigma = 3.0$, $\phi = 0.6$, $\alpha = 1.0$, $\beta = 0.1$ (b) Plot of the mean $\langle x \rangle_{st}$ against the tumor population x at varying τ . Remaining parameter values are fixed at $\lambda = 3.0$, $D = 2.0$, $\sigma = 3.0$, $\phi = 0.6$, $\alpha = 1.0$, $\beta = 0.1$ (units are arbitrary).

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. (a) Plot of the mean $\langle x \rangle_{st}$ against the tumor population x at varying λ . Remaining parameter values are fixed at $\tau = 0.1$, $D = 2.0$, $\sigma = 1.0$, $\phi = 0.6$, $a = 1.0$, $b = 0.1$ (b) Plot of the mean $\langle x \rangle_{st}$ against the tumor population x at varying λ . Remaining parameter values are fixed at $\tau = 1.0$, $D = 2.0$, $\sigma = 1.0$, $\phi = 0.6$, $\alpha = 1.0$, $\beta = 0.1$ (units are arbitrary).

5. Conclusion

We have investigated the steady state properties for the tumor response to the non-immunogenic tumor microenvironmental factors in the presence of immune response. The research reveals that tumor microenvironment is

such a critical environment with respect to tumor progression, and is an embodiment of competing biological processes that interact with the tumor cells constantly and each with a specific biological function. We find that the correlation time strength τ and the immune strength λ have opposite effect on both the steady state distribution $P_{st}(x)$ and the stationary mean $\langle x \rangle_{st}$ of the tumor population. Moreover, both the steady state distribution $P_{st}(x)$ and the mean $\langle x \rangle_{st}$ of the tumor population increases at increasing correlation time τ , and decreases at increasing immune response strength λ . The result indicates that the correlation time strength τ is a factor responsible for the growth effect exerted by the non-immunogenic component of tumor microenvironment. Further, the result also indicates that the stronger the immune response λ the weaker is the growth effect exerted by the correlation time strength τ on the tumor growth system.

Acknowledgment

The authors acknowledge support from Tertiary Education Trust Fund Federal Republic of Nigeria. Ibrahim Mu'awiyya Idris conceived the idea, derived the analytic result, contributed in numerical simulation and manuscript preparation. Ibrahim Lawal Kane did the numerical simulation, result discussion and manuscript preparation.

References

- [1] Andrej Fulinski and Tomasz Telejko. On the Effect of Interference of Additive and Multiplicative Noises. *Physics Letters A*. Vol. 152, No. 1,2 (1991), 11-14.
- [2] C J Wang and D C Mei. Transport and current reversal in a periodic system driven by cross-correlated noises. *Physica Scripta*. 76 (2007), 131–133.
- [3] Bao-Quan Ai, Wei Chen, Xian-Ju Wang, Guo-Tao Liu, De-Hua Wen, Hui-Zhang Xie and Liang-Gang Liu. Noise in an insect outbreak model. *Chin. J. Phys.* Vol. 41, No. 4 (2003), 1-8.
- [4] Weirong Zhong, Yuanzhi Shao, Zhenhui He. Stochastic resonance in the growth of a tumor induced by correlated noises. *Chinese Science Bulletin*. Volume 50, Issue 20 (2005), 2273–2275.
- [5] D.C. Mei, C.W. Xie and L. Zhang. The stationary properties and the state transition of the tumor cell growth mode. *Eur. Phys. J. B* 41 (2004), 107–112.
- [6] Anita Behera and S. Francesca C. O'Rourke. The Effect of Correlated Noise in a Gompertz Tumor Growth Model. *Brazilian Journal of Physics*, Vol. 38, No. 2 (2008), 272-278.
- [7] X.-M. Zhang and B.-Q. Ai. Genotype selection model with two time-correlated white noises. *Eur. Phys. J. B* 73 (2010), 433–437.
- [8] Xue-Mei Liu, Hui-Zhang Xie, Liang-Gang Liu and Zhi-Bing Li. Effect of Multiplicative and Additive Noise On Genetic Transcriptional Regulatory Mechanism. *Physica A* 388 (2009), 392-398.
- [9] Chen Li-Mei, Cao Li, Wu Da-Jin and Ge Guo-Qin. Effect on Intensity Correlation Time by Input Signal in a Single-Mode Laser with Bias Signal Modulation. *Commun. Theor. Phys.* 44 (2005), 638–642.
- [10] Zhu Ping. Dynamical Properties of a Bistable System Driven by Cross-Correlated Additive and Multiplicative Colored Noises. *Chinese Journal of Physics*, Vol. 44, No. 2 (2006), 117-126.
- [11] Wu Da-jin, Cao Li and K Sheng-Zhi. Bistable kinetic model driven by correlated noises: Steady-state analysis. *Physical Review E*, Vol. 50, No. 4 (1994), 2496-2502.
- [12] Bao-Quan Ai, Xian-Ju Wang, Guo-Tao Liu, and Liang-Gang Liu. Correlated Noise in a Logistic Growth Model. *Physical Review E* 67 022903 (2003), 1-3.

- [13] Thomas Bose and Steffen Trimper. Stochastic Model for Tumor Growth with Immunization. *Physical Review E* 79 (2009), 051903.
- [14] Wang Can-Jun, Li Di and Mei Dong-Cheng. Pure Multiplicative Noises Induced Population Extinction in an Anti-tumor Model under Immune Surveillance. *Commun. Theor. Phys.* 52 (2009), 463–467.
- [15] Chunhua Zeng and Hua Wang. Colored Noise Enhanced Stability in a Tumor Cell Growth System Under Immune Response. *Journal of Statistical Physics*, 141 (2010), 889–908.
- [16] Chunhua Zeng, Xiaofeng Zhou and Shufen Tao. Cross-correlation Enhanced Stability in a Tumor Cell Growth Model With Immune Surveillance Driven by Cross-correlated Noises. *J. Phys. A: Math. Theor.* 42, 495002 (2009), 1-8.
- [17] Isaac P. Witz. The Tumor Microenvironment: The Making of a Paradigm. *Journal of Cancer Microenvironment*, No.2 Suppl-1 (2009), 9-17.
- [18] Zhang Xuejing, Daotai Nie, and Subhas Chakrabarty. Growth factors in tumor microenvironment. *Frontiers in bioscience: a journal and virtual library*, 15 (2010), 151-165.
- [19] Witz, Isaac P. Yin-yang. Activities and vicious cycles in the tumor microenvironment. *Cancer research*, Vol. 68, No. 1 (2008), 9-13.
- [20] Strell Carina, Helene Rundqvist, and Arne Ostman. Fibroblasts-a key host cell type in tumor initiation, progression and metastasis. *Uppsala journal of medical sciences* 117, No. 2 (2012), 187-195.
- [21] Ibrahim Mu’awiyya Idris and Mohd Rizam Abu Bakar. Effect of tumor microenvironmental factors on tumor growth dynamics modeled by correlated colored noises with colored cross-correlation. *Physica A* 453 (2016), 298–304.
- [22] Kwara Nantomah. On some properties of the sigmoid function. *Asia Matematika*, Volume 3 Issue 1, (2019) pages:79-90.
- [23] R. Lefever and R. Garay. Local Description of Immune Tumor Rejection, *Biomathematics and Cell Kinetics*, eds. A.J. Valleron and P.D.M. Macdonald, Elsevier, North-Holland (1978), 333.
- [24] N.G Van Kampen. *Stochastic Differential Equations*. *Physics Reports*, Vol.24, Issue 3 (1976), 171-228.
- [25] Gardiner, C.W. *Handbook of Stochastic Methods for Physics, Chemistry and the Natural Sciences*, Second ed., Springer-Verlag, Berlin (1985).
- [26] H. Risken, *The Fokker Planck Equation Method of Solution and Application*. Springer-Verlag, Berlin (1996).
- [27] E.A. Novikov. Functionals and the Random Force Method in Turbulence Theory. *Soviet Physics Jetp*, Vol.20, No.5 (1965), 1290-1294.
- [28] Ronald F. Fox. Functional-calculus Approach to Stochastic Differential Equations. *Physical Review A*, Vol.33, No.1 (1986), 467-476.
- [29] Peter Hanggi, Thomas J. Mroczkowski, Frank Moss, and Peter VE McClintock. Bistability driven by colored noise: Theory and experiment. *Physical Review A* 32, No. 1 (1985), 695-698.
- [30] Hanna E., Quick J., and Libutti S. The Tumor Microenvironment: a Novel Target for Cancer Therapy. *Oral Diseases*, Vol.15, No.1 (2009): 18-17.
- [31] G. Devipriya. Analytic solution of dengue model with maturation delay by homotopy perturbation method. *Asia Matematika*, Volume 1, Issue 2, (2017) pages: 49-60.